

Atmosphere and Awe: VR Worlds Inspired by Romantic Art Landscapes

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Abstract: A common and very natural aim of virtual reality (VR) world designers is to recreate reality, or to create a possible reality that once existed, or will potentially exist. This recreation of realism is extremely successful in areas such as VR documentaries, simulations, education and training, where convincing realism increases the engagement of the participant. The ability of VR to create a sense of immersive presence has been widely discussed and established (Slater and Wilbur 1997, Witmer and Singer 1998, Schuemie 2001), and the visual experience of the 360 degree world is an inherent and essential component. This paper seeks to focus on the teaching of the design of the VR landscape, in particular the atmospheric and dramatic landscape that may be realistic, or fictional, or fantastic, the relationship to cinematic experience, and its inheritance from the landscape painters of the Romantic Art movement. The Romantic Art movement ran from ca 1800 to 1850, and has been very influential upon the popular immersive spaces of film and computer games. The artists of this movement were fascinated with the emotional and spiritual aspects of the landscape, emphasising atmosphere, mood, and the representation of the fantastic, all things that are ideal for VR.

Romantic Art Landscapes

The Romantic art movement originated in Europe towards the end of the 18th century, peaking from around 1800 to 1850. Partly as a reaction against the industrialization and rationalism of the industrial revolution, Romanticism embraced emotion and individualism, idealising nature, the spectacle, and man's place in the universe. The landscape painters of the Romantic period were fascinated with the emotional and spiritual aspects of the landscape, emphasising atmosphere, mood, and the representation of the sublime. These artworks employed qualities that today would be considered majestic, awe-inspiring, or possibly “epic”, expressing individuality and idealised representation of a Classical heritage. (Artincontex 2022).

The Romantic art movement has been very influential upon the conceptual art and the cinematography for cinema and game landscapes. Many of the rendering principles are commonly visible, particular when scale and environmental impressiveness is required. E.g. as seen in the advertising for the Lord of the Rings (Figure 1).

Figure 1: *Fanciful landscape* by Thomas Doughty (1834) and *Lord of the Rings* movie official poster (2001)

The Romantic artists established a set of compositional principles that shaped the way they approached their work. In his book, Sir Alfred East (1906), a British painter who was influenced by the Romantic landscape painters, provides a detailed analysis of their composition techniques. He discusses topics such as the use of colour, light, and atmosphere to create mood and emotion in landscape paintings, combining realism and artistic interpretation. Some of the most important of these principles include:

Emphasis on atmosphere:

Romantic landscape painters sought to convey a sense of atmosphere and mood in their work. They used techniques such as colour and light to create a sense of mist, fog, or light that imbued the landscapes with a sense of mystery and spirituality. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Albert Bierstadt - *A Storm in the Rocky Mountains, Mt. Rosalie* (1866), and Louwrens Hanedoes - *Hilly Landscape with a Ruin* (1849).

Use of perspective:

These artists often used unconventional and exaggerated perspectives to create a sense of instability and unpredictability in their paintings, and to convey a sense of the vastness of the natural world. (Figure 1)

Dynamic composition:

Romantic landscapes are often composed in such a way as to create a sense of movement and dynamism within the scene. This can be achieved through the use of sweeping curves, dramatic contrasts of light and dark, and the positioning of the horizon line.

Emphasis on the sublime:

Romantic art was fascinated with depicting the sublime: the quality of greatness beyond measure, outstanding spiritual, intellectual, or moral worth. Artists sought to capture the awe-inspiring beauty of the natural world depicting grand and imposing landscapes such as mountains, forests, and seascapes, and including spiritual and philosophical symbols (Figure 3).

Representation of human presence:

Many Romantic landscape painters sought to include evidence of human presence in their work, often in the form of small figures or structures, such as churches or bridges. This served to emphasize the smallness and insignificance of man in the face of the grandeur of nature (Figure 3).

Use of the picturesque:

Romantic landscape painters often sought to capture the beauty and tranquillity of the rural countryside, and they often used techniques such as soft focus, delicate colour harmonies, and idyllic landscapes to create a sense of calm and peacefulness in their paintings (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Louise-Joséphine Sarazin de Belmont, *The Roman Theater at Taormina*, (1828) and Robert Duncanson, *Scotch Highlands* (c1848-1852)

These compositional principles reflect the Romantic movement's fascination with the emotional and spiritual aspects of the landscape, and its emphasis on atmosphere, mood, and the representation of the sublime. By employing these principles, Romantic landscape painters sought to create powerful and evocative images that captured the emotional impact of the natural world.

In terms of compositional devices, the Romantic artists relied heavily on several techniques to support their mood pieces.

- The sun is usually visible in frame. This highlights the majesty of the sun and the smallness of mankind. It also allows for glow effects, such as haze, fog and bloom – the blurred glow effect from reflective objects.
- The sun's rays are descending onto the subject. Technically this illuminates the focus point, but also emotionally highlights the light from above, now-a-days sometimes referred to as “God rays”.
- The scene is composed of layers – foreground, mid-ground, background and sky, or even more levels of layers. This enhances the theatrical and dramatic impression. The same approach is used when dressing a theatre stage.
- Foreground objects are in silhouette. This is also a staging effect, framing the scene and emphasising the experience of viewing into the landscape, similar to viewing through a window.
- Human figures are very often small, dwarfed by the majesty of nature. Even when the human objects are larger, they are still located inside the majestic and dominating landscape.

The Romantic landscape painters also observed the principles of landscape composition, such as the rule of thirds, (Stewart 2020) balance, contrast, juxtaposition, and other principles commonly applied by landscape artists and concept artists for cinema and games (Bellard 2022) (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Computer Game *Shadow of the Colossus* (Sony 2005) and Computer game *Horizon Zero Dawn* (Sony 2017).

Designing the action

Before the experiential style of a digital environment can be assembled, the practical function needs to be defined. In the case of VR, consideration is first given to participant movement, and this is largely determined by the VR experience of the targeted VR audience. When targeting novices, it is common to place the VR participant in a static location. The environment can then be built in one direction, a 180 degree view, or surrounding the participant in a full 360 degree view. If the designer observes principles of theatre staging, objects close to the participant are generally small in size and positioned low so as to not obscure the mid and background. As objects are placed further away, they increasingly gain in size. When combined with principles of Romantic Art landscape, such as scale, lighting and atmosphere, an immersive VR environment for a static participant can become very effective.

In terms of visual narrative, a fixed location does require some changes to narrative techniques. While items and symbols are still effective, there is no way to move the participant through a visual story. Instead, the visual story is may be required to move past the static player. This is possibly less natural than a walking exploration, but a story that is revealed as it passes the player can be very effective, generating a sensation of being a witness. For example, *Surge* is a music video created by Arjan van Meerten and produced by Dutch studio House of Secrets (2016). The participant is placed in a static position in a geometric world where they view dancing cubes forming themselves into various life-like arrangements. The work concludes with a parade of towering figures that degrade as they walk past the participant. The viewer experiences one continuous view, while events change around them. The viewer does not interact in this case, instead the experience is more like witnessing an event. *Surge*'s version of a story is to present ideas that change over time, all set to music

Figure 5: *Surge* music video by Arjan van Meerten (2016)

For more experienced participants, that is, those with VR or computer game experience, a moving VR participation is acceptable. This then, is very similar to designing an environment for a computer game, although with higher awareness of player speed and most probably less interaction. Most 3D computer games that simulate a first-person view offer some free exploration within a linear game pathway. Usually there are goals and rewards to be achieved, and this helps to guide the player along a pathway to success. Some games are more open, allowing for open exploration, with a less linear narrative development. Both paradigms can be successful for VR worlds.

The nature of the student group for this project

The student examples have been selected from two classes: Class 1 was a post-graduate workshop style class, designed to introduce students to VR environment building, and class 2 was in the game design pathway. All had basic to intermediate level of experience with environment building software and techniques. Some students used Autodesk Maya for 3D assets building, whereas others were allowed to download assets from the Unreal

Marketplace. Both classes used Unreal Engine 5 for environment building.

Both classes receive lectures and instructions which included an overview of Romantic Art landscape painting, as well as principles of navigation within a landscape. These navigation principles were founded on the work by Kevin Lynch in his book *Image of the City*, where he describes 5 elements that are required in order to provide a cognitive understanding of the world in order to feel oriented and be able to navigate. Kevin Lynch argues that the physical form of cities can have a profound impact on the way that people understand and experience their urban environment. He argues that people form mental images of the city based on their experiences and observations, and that these mental images play a crucial role in shaping their sense of place and their sense of belonging within the city. Lynch identifies five key elements that are organised and arranged within the urban fabric that have a significant impact on the way that people experience and navigate the city.

These elements are: (Figure 6)

1. Pathways – Channels for navigation movement
2. Edges – Indicate district limits. Gates, walls, cliffs, rivers. Often vertical barriers. Like paths, can be used to direct players.
3. Districts – A region identifier. Districts should have unique visual identity – colour, function – and include natural districts such as forest, desert, mountains.
4. Nodes – Focal points for travel. Homes, hubs, intersections, gathering points, town square, focus points of use, train stations, airports.
5. Landmarks. – Single, localised. Memorable. Provides reference points and orientation. Provides a knowable and reassuring constants when exploring.

Figure 6: Lynch's five elements of city navigation

When designing a digital immersive environment, Lynch's elements provide guidance for the participant viewpoint at a fundamental level. Should the participant viewpoint be 1: Top-down – By plan, big picture, architectural, large-scale, possibly with zoom in and out, or 2: By in-world discovery – requiring engagement by the participant to move through the world to reveal, discover and learn.

A final consideration was the nature of the participant movement. The game class students simply adopted fast paced first-person and third-person viewpoints. This then required a walkable, or runnable scale to their environments. Distances were determined by how long they wanted their players to spend moving from place to place. The VR students had slightly different considerations, imposed by the nature of VR, and were presented with three methods of movement: Static, pre-determined pathways, and free movement. Most of the students chose pre-determined pathways and free movement, reasoning that VR movement was very similar to movement in a first-

person computer game. The students felt little obligation to accommodate filmic cuts and edits, or to feel concerned about possible nausea inducing motion.

In the computer lab tutorial situation the principles from Romantic Art and Lynch's elements were applied in class in the technical training exercises. For example, the lighting demonstrations included atmospheric haze and fog, beams of light, coloured artistic skies, glow and dark shadows. The students were shown how to manipulate various default settings such as for the sun and sky to create original, multi-coloured, skiescapes. These manipulative tips and tricks were taught alongside various tutorials about operating the software.

Figure 5: Instructor demonstration. Left: the in-world view, Right: the world under construction.

Student results

The final student results demonstrated an excellent understanding and application of the Romantic Art Principles to the digital immersive world context.

Artemis

This environment follows a nomad as they explore an abandoned underground village in search of a God-like protector, Artemis (Figure 6). The environment needed to invoke a feeling of a subterranean cavern that was once great, but has since degraded into ruins. The diffused lighting descends from somewhere above, but is not strong enough to suggest sunlight. The path is littered with ruins from a greater time, as the player follows a pre-determined pathway towards the guardian shrine.

Figure 6: Student work: *Artemis* and *UQA*

UQA

In UQA (Figure 6) the player is required to find a lost robot, that unfortunately has run away and become violent. This game prototype largely takes place in a forest, giving the player a very clear pathway. The final scene is situated in a clearing, with a 360 degree area of movement, and avoidance of the violent robot.

Zero Dusk

Zero Dusk was a project by three students who all worked to their strengths. The story line is about moving through a large industrial space and attempting to avoid awakening a giant robot, who naturally, awakens and suggests a boss fight scene. This project is a game cinematic, that is, it is a rendered movie set in the game engine, and is not a playable game as such. It functions more like a cut scene or a trailer. This cinematic demonstrates an excellent sense of atmosphere, with strong lighting, scale, juxtaposition, and the overall creation of an awe-inspiring scene.

Figure 7: Student work: *Zero Dusk*

Shelter

The Shelter project (Figure 8) is a 1st person walking simulator where the VR participant discovers a utopian world. The students attempted to construct a “Garden of Eden” – an ideal garden that follows the more natural intimate principles of Romantic Art landscapes. The VR participant is limited to a pre-determined pathway, and so, ideally, are able to view the garden always at optimal angles.

Art Gallery

The Art Gallery (Figure 8) is a VR walking simulator that takes the participant through an architectural interpretation of an art gallery. This project also restricts the VR participant to specific pathways, ensuring the best views of the imaginative forms. While less of an environmental vista than other projects, the students still attempted to employ some of the principles of romantic art, such as scale, juxtaposition and atmosphere.

Figure 8: Student work: *Shelter and Art Gallery*

Summary

Drawing connections between Romantic Art, city navigation principles, and digital immersive worlds proved to be of great value in expanding the visual language of these students. In some cases they appeared to apply these principles directly, and in other cases it was more subtle. It was enlightening for the students to comprehend how the current visual culture of their favourite games and movies have their origin in an art movement of over 100 years ago. Many students were also enlightened to see the connections between the various visual techniques and their intellectual and emotional meanings. Now that these students have a clearer comprehension of these techniques, it is hoped that they are able to apply them with greater judgement and effectiveness. Like all visual language, an understanding of the source empowers the artist to create new experiences to share with their audience.

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